

Analysis and Application of Branch and Bound Technique for Minimizing the Make-Span of a Flow Shop

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Abstract: How to schedule jobs on machines subject to certain constraints to optimize some objective functions is actually a scheduling problem. Scheduling specifies when and on which machine each job is to be executed. This research work describes the algorithm for branch and bound techniques for minimizing the make-span of a flow shop. The flow shop problem with make span criterion can be shown by $n/m/F/c_{max}$ or equivalently $F//c_{max}$ where both show a (n-job, m-machine) flow shop problem with make span criterion that can be defined as completion time at which all jobs complete processing or equivalently as maximum completion time of jobs. The objective of this present study is to obtain the optimal schedule of all jobs which minimize the total elapsed time using branch and bound technique. The optimal sequence is job1—job2—job4—job6—job5—job3. Finally, it was realized from the research that the total elapsed time or make-span is 8657.5mins.

Key words: Flow shop, Branch and bound techniques, Optimal sequence, Jobs, Machines

INTRODUCTION

Mouka foam involves in the production of six different types of products for customers. The major challenge of the company is to determine the order in which the different jobs must be processed to minimize the make-span. The way in which orders are received from customers is in a random process. At present, there is no scientific approach for determining the order in which the different jobs must be scheduled for production using its facilities. Increase in cost of production and inability to meet customers' demands are some of the challenges being faced by the company since the scheduling is done at the discretion of the production manager without the application of any technique. Thus, there is a great need to develop a technique that can minimize the make-span of producing the different jobs. The uses of sequence-dependent scheduling are commonly found in most manufacturing environments. For instance, in Mouka Foam Company, machines must be adjusted whenever there is change in dimensions of end products. Thus, the process is a multi-stage production system (i.e., flow shop). In this situation, a sequence-dependent setup times play a major role and must be considered when modeling the problem.

A flow shop as the name implies is a multi-stage production system with more than one parallel machine at each stage and all products going through the system unidirectional (i.e., stage 1, then stage 2, and so on) (Balasubramanian and Grossmann, 2002; Chen *et al.*, 2014). The area of flow-shop problems,

scheduling theory has been strongly influenced by Johnson's early works (Pranzo, 2004). There are thousands of research work on different optimal procedures and heuristics for solving the flow shop scheduling problem and its variants (Nawaz et al., 1983). The regular flow-shop problem consists of two main elements (Balasubramanian and Grossmann, 2004);

- i. A group of M machines and
- ii. A set of N jobs to be processed on this group of machine

Each of the N jobs has the same ordering of machines for its process sequence. Each job can be processed on one and only one machine at a time (which means no job splitting), and each machine can process only one job at a time. Each job is processed only once on each machine. Operations are not pre-emptable and set-up times of operations are independent of the sequences and therefore can be included in the processing time. The scheduling problem is to specify the order and timing of the processing of the jobs on machines, with an objective or objectives respecting above-mentioned assumptions (Bassett et al., 1996; Ben-Tal and Nemirovski, 2000; Bonfill et al., 2005; Jia and Ierapetritou, 2000). Francesco and Raffaele (2008) introduces an additive branch-and-bound algorithm for two variants of the pickup and delivery traveling salesman problem in which loading and unloading operations have to be performed either in a last-In-First-Out (LIFO) or in a First-In-First-Out (FIFO) order. He makes use of two relaxations within the additive approach via the assignment problem and the shortest spanning r-arborescence problem. The quality of the lower bounds was further improve by a set of elimination rules applied at each node of the search tree to remove from the problem arcs that cannot belong to feasible solutions because of precedence relationships. Also, three integer programming formulations and a branch-and-cut algorithm for the Traveling Salesman Problem with Pickup and Delivery with LIFO Loading (TSPPDL) (TSPPDL) were introduced by Cordeau et al. (2008). This approach is based on the Traveling Salesman Problem with Pickup and Delivery (TSPPD) formulation of Ruland and Rodin (1997) and relies on an exponential number of constraints to impose the LIFO policy. Several families of valid inequalities are also used to strengthen the formulation. Exact separation procedures are used to identify violated subtour elimination constraints, precedence constraints and LIFO constraints, while heuristic separation procedures are used for the other families of inequalities. This algorithm is able to solve most instances with up to 43 vertices and some instances with 51 vertices in less than 60 minutes of computing time. However, in this present research work, a scheduling technique was applied to determine the order in which the jobs manufactured by Mouka foam company are produced in order for the make-span of flow shop to be minimized.

METHODOLOGY

A. Flow Shop

In a flow-shop, the work in a job is broken down into separate tasks called operations, and each operation is performed at a different machine. In this context, a job is a collection of operations with a special precedence structure. In particular, each operation after the first has exactly one direct predecessor and each operation before the last has exactly one direct successor, as shown in the flow chart (Fig. 1). Thus, each job requires a specific sequence of operations to be carried out for the job to be complete (Kallrath, 2000).

Fig. 1 Flow chart

Data Collection

The data used in this research work was collected from Mouka Foam Nigeria Limited. The data used was based on the major activities in each stage of foam production. These are:

A. *Machines*

- i. Foaming Area (Stage 1, Machine 1)
- ii. Fork-lift truck (Stage 2, Machine 2)
- iii. Curing Hall (Stage 3, Machine 3)
- iv. Slicing (Conversion) (Stage 4, Machine 4)
- v. Tape edge Section (Stage 5, Machine 5)
- vi. Nyloning section (Stage 6, Machine 6)

B. *Processing Time*

Table 1 shows the data of six (6) jobs to six (machines) flow-shop problem with the respective processing time of the jobs on each machine.

Table 1 Processing time of jobs on each machine

Machines	Jobs					
	1	2	3	4	5	6
M ₁	1.5	2.0	1440	3.0	8.0	3.0
M ₂	1.7	2.5	1440	3.2	12.0	3.2
M ₃	1.9	2.8	1440	3.5	13.0	3.5
M ₄	2.1	2.6	1440	3.6	13.5	3.8
M ₅	2.5	3.2	1440	3.8	15.0	4.0
M ₆	4.2	2.2	1440	5.0	20.0	5.0

Data Analysis

In this research work, branch and bound approach was adopted. The branch and bound approach is a useful method for solving many combinatorial problems. The method involves two fundamental procedures. Namely;

- i. Branching which is the process of partitioning a large problem into two or more sub-problems
- ii. Bounding is the process of calculating a lower bound on the optimal solution of a given sub-problem.

The branching procedure replaces an original problem by a set of new problems that are:

- i. Mutually exclusive and collectively exhaustive sub-problems of the original,
- ii. Partially solved versions of the original, and
- iii. Smaller problems than the original.

The bounding procedure calculates a lower bound on the solution to each sub-problem generated in the branching process. It is based on the assumption that;

- i. Suppose that at some intermediate stage a complete solution has been obtained that has an associated performance measure Z.
- ii. Suppose also that a sub-problem encountered in the branching process has an associated lower bound $b > Z$.

Then the sub-problem need not be considered any further in the search for an optimum. That is, no matter how the sub-problem is resolved, the resulting solution can never have a value better than Z. When such a sub-problem is found, its branch is said to be fathomed. By not branching any further from fathomed branches, the enumeration process is curtailed because feasible solutions of a fathomed sub-problem are evaluated implicitly rather than being constructed explicitly.

A complete solution that allows branches to be fathomed is called a trial solution. It may be obtained at the very outset by applying a heuristic procedure (i.e. a sub-problem method capable of obtaining good solution with limited computational effort); or it can be obtained in the course of the tree search, perhaps by pursuing the tree directly to the bottom as rapidly as possible.

Notation

The illustration of how these concepts are applied in the flow shop problem is shown with the followings notations. When given n jobs to be processed on six stage flow shop scheduling problem, the following notations apply;

- A_i = Processing time for job i on machine A
- B_i = Processing time for job i on machine B
- C_i = Processing time for job i on machine C
- D_i = Processing time for job i on machine D
- E_i = Processing time for job i on machine E
- F_i = Processing time for job i on machine F
- C_{ij} = Completion time of job i on machine j
- J_r = Partial schedule of r scheduled jobs
- J_r' = The set of remaining (n-r) free jobs

Mathematical Development

Consider n jobs say i = 1, 2, 3...,n are processed on six machines A, B, C,D,E and F in the order ABCDEF. A job i (i = 1, 2, 3...,n) has processing time A_i, B_i, C_i, D_i, E_i and F_i on each machine respectively. The mathematical model of the problem in matrix form can be stated as shown in Table 2.

Table 2. The matrix form of flow-shop problem

Jobs	Machine A	Machine B	Machine C	Machine D	Machine E	Machine F
i	A _i	B _i	C _i	D _i	E _i	F _i
1	A ₁	B ₁	C ₁	D ₁	E ₁	F ₁
2	A ₂	B ₂	C ₂	D ₂	E ₂	F ₂
3	A ₃	B ₃	C ₃	D ₃	E ₃	F ₃
4	A ₄	B ₄	C ₄	D ₄	E ₄	F ₄
5	A ₅	B ₅	C ₅	D ₅	E ₅	F ₅
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n	A _n	B _n	C _n	D _n	E _n	F _n

The objective is to obtain the optimal schedule of all jobs which minimize the total elapsed time using branch and bound technique.

Algorithm of Branch and Bound

Step 1: Calculate

- (i) $G_1 = t(J_r, 1) + \sum_{i \in J_r'} A_i + \min_{i \in J_r'} (B_i + C_i + D_i + E_i + F_i)$
- (ii) $G_2 = t(J_r, 2) + \sum_{i \in J_r'} B_i + \min_{i \in J_r'} (C_i + D_i + E_i + F_i)$
- (iii) $G_3 = t(J_r, 3) + \sum_{i \in J_r'} C_i + \min_{i \in J_r'} (D_i + E_i + F_i)$
- (iv) $G_4 = t(J_r, 4) + \sum_{i \in J_r'} D_i + \min_{i \in J_r'} (E_i + F_i)$
- (v) $G_5 = t(j_r, 5) + \sum_{i \in J_r'} E_i + \min_{i \in J_r'} (F_i)$

$$(vi) \quad G_6 = t(J_r, 6) + \sum_{i \in J'_r} F_i$$

Step 2: Calculate

$G = \max [G_1, G_2, G_3, G_4, G_5, G_6]$, evaluate G first for the n classes of permutations, for these starting with 1, 2, 3.....n respectively, having labeled the appropriate vertices of the scheduling tree by these values.

Step 3: Now explore the vertex with lowest label. Evaluate G for the (n-1) subclasses starting with this vertex and again concentrate on the lowest label vertex. It was a continuous process, until we reach the end of the tree represented by two single permutations, for which the total work duration is evaluated. Thus we get the optimal schedule of the jobs.

Step 4: We prepare in-out table for the optimal sequence obtained in step 3 and it will give the minimum total elapsed time corresponding to the make span.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The analysis of data presented in Table 1 and Table 2 which comprised of six jobs to six machines is carried out by using the branch and bound algorithm given below.

Step 1: Calculate

For $J_1 = (1)$, then $J' (1) = 1.5, 3.2, 5.1, 7.2, 9.7, 13.9$

$$G_1 = 1.5 + 1456 + 13.3 = 1470.8$$

$$G_2 = 3.2 + 1460.9 + 10.8 = 1474.9$$

$$G_3 = 5.1 + 1462.8 + 8 = 1475.9$$

$$G_4 = 7.2 + 1463.5 + 5.4 = 1476.1$$

$$G_5 = 9.7 + 1466 + 2.2 = 1477.9$$

$$G_6 = 13.9 + 1472.2 + 0 = 1486.1$$

$$G = \max [G_1, G_2, G_3, G_4, G_5, G_6],$$

$$\therefore LB (1) = 1486.1$$

For $J_2 = (2)$, then $J' (2) = 2, 4.5, 7.3, 9.9, 13.1, 15.3$

$$G_1 = 2 + 1455.5 + 12.4 = 1469.9$$

$$G_2 = 4.5 + 1460.1 + 10.7 = 1475.3$$

$$G_3 = 7.3 + 1461.9 + 8.8 = 1478$$

$$G_4 = 9.9 + 1463 + 6.7 = 1479.6$$

$$G_5 = 13.1 + 1465.3 + 4.2 = 1482.6$$

$$G_6 = 15.3 + 1474.2 + 0 = 1489.5$$

$$G = \max [G_1, G_2, G_3, G_4, G_5, G_6],$$

$$\therefore LB (2) = 1489.5$$

For $J_3 = (3)$, then $J' (3) = 1440, 2880, 4320, 5760, 7200, 8640$

$$G_1 = 1440 + 17.5 + 12.4 = 1469.9$$

$$G_2 = 2880 + 22.6 + 10.7 = 2913.3$$

$$G_3 = 4320 + 24.7 + 8.8 = 4353.5$$

$$G_4 = 5760 + 25.6 + 6.7 = 5792.3$$

$$G_5 = 7200 + 28.5 + 4.2 = 7232.7$$

$$G_6 = 8640 + 36.4 + 0 = 8676.6$$

$$G = \max [G_1, G_2, G_3, G_4, G_5, G_6],$$

$$\therefore \text{LB (3)} = 8676.4$$

For $J_4 = (4)$, then $J' (4) = 3, 6.2, 9.7, 13.3, 17.1, 22.1$

$$G_1 = 3 + 1454.5 + 12.4 = 1469.9$$

$$G_2 = 6.2 + 1459.4 + 10.7 = 1476.3$$

$$G_3 = 9.7 + 1461.2 + 8.8 = 1479.7$$

$$G_4 = 13.3 + 1462 + 6.7 = 1482$$

$$G_5 = 17.1 + 1464.7 + 4.2 = 1486$$

$$G_6 = 22.1 + 1471.4 + 0 = 1493.5$$

$$G = \max [G_1, G_2, G_3, G_4, G_5, G_6],$$

$$\therefore \text{LB (4)} = 1493.5$$

For $J_5 = (5)$, then $J' (5) = 8, 20, 33, 46.5, 61.5, 81.5$

$$G_1 = 8 + 1449.5 + 12.4 = 1469.9$$

$$G_2 = 20 + 1450.6 + 10.7 = 1481.3$$

$$G_3 = 33 + 1451.7 + 8.8 = 1493.5$$

$$G_4 = 46.5 + 1452.1 + 6.7 = 1505.3$$

$$G_5 = 61.5 + 1453.5 + 4.2 = 1519.2$$

$$G_6 = 81.5 + 1456.4 + 0 = 1537.9$$

$$G = \max [G_1, G_2, G_3, G_4, G_5, G_6],$$

$$\therefore \text{LB (5)} = 1537.9$$

For $J_6 = (6)$, then $J' (6) = 3, 6.2, 9.7, 13.5, 17.5, 22.5$

$$G_1 = 3 + 1454.5 + 12.4 = 1469.9$$

$$G_2 = 6.2 + 1459.4 + 10.7 = 1476.3$$

$$G_3 = 9.7 + 1461.2 + 8.8 = 1479.7$$

$$G_4 = 13.5 + 1461.8 + 6.7 = 1482$$

$$G_5 = 17.5 + 1464.5 + 4.2 = 1486.2$$

$$G_6 = 22.5 + 1471.4 + 0 = 1493.9$$

$$G = \max [G_1, G_2, G_3, G_4, G_5, G_6],$$

$$\therefore \text{LB (6)} = 1493.9$$

Step 2 and 3: Now branch from $J_1 = (1)$, since it has the minimum Lower Bound (LB).

For $J_2 = (1-2)$, then $J' (1-2) = 3.5, 6, 8.8, 11.4, 14.6, 16.8$

$$G_1 = 3.5 + 1454 + 19.1 = 1476.6$$

$$G_2 = 6 + 1458.4 + 15.9 = 1480.3$$

$$G_3 = 8.8 + 1460 + 12.4 = 1481.2$$

$$G_4 = 11.4 + 1460.9 + 8.8 = 1481.1$$

$$G_5 = 14.6 + 1462.8 + 5 = 1482.4$$

$$G_6 = 16.8 + 1470 + 0 = 1486.8$$

$$G = \max [G_1, G_2, G_3, G_4, G_5, G_6],$$

$$\therefore \text{LB (1-2)} = 1486.8$$

For $J_3 = (1-3)$, then $J' (1-3) = 1441.5, 2881.5, 4321.5, 5761.5, 7201.5, 8641.5$

$$G_1 = 1441.5 + 16 + 13.3 = 1470.8$$

$$G_2 = 2881.5 + 20.9 + 10.8 = 2913.2$$

$$G_3 = 4321.5 + 22.8 + 8 = 4352.3$$

$$G_4 = 5761.5 + 23.5 + 5.4 = 5790.4$$

$$G_5 = 7201.5 + 26 + 2.2 = 7229.7$$

$$G_6 = 8641.5 + 32.2 + 0 = 8673.7$$

$$G = \max [G_1, G_2, G_3, G_4, G_5, G_6],$$

$$\therefore \text{LB (1-3)} = 8673.7$$

For $J_4 = (1-4)$, then $J' (1-4) = 4.5, 7.7, 11.2, 14.8, 8, 18.6, 23.6$

$$G_1 = 4.5 + 1453 + 13.3 = 1470.8$$

$$G_2 = 7.7 + 1457.7 + 10.8 = 1476.2$$

$$G_3 = 11.2 + 1459.3 + 8 = 1478.5$$

$$G_4 = 14.8 + 1459.9 + 5.4 = 1480.1$$

$$G_5 = 18.6 + 1462.2 + 2.2 = 1483$$

$$G_6 = 23.6 + 1467.2 + 0 = 1490.8$$

$$G = \max [G_1, G_2, G_3, G_4, G_5, G_6],$$

$$\therefore \text{LB (1-4)} = 1490.8$$

For $J_5 = (1-5)$, then $J' (1-5) = 9.5, 21.5, 34.5, 48.63, 83$

$$G_1 = 9.5 + 1448 + 13.3 = 1470.8$$

$$G_2 = 21.5 + 1448.9 + 10.8 = 1481.2$$

$$G_3 = 34.5 + 1449.8 + 8 = 1492.3$$

$$G_4 = 48 + 1450 + 5.4 = 1503.4$$

$$G_5 = 63 + 1451 + 2.2 = 1516.2$$

$$G_6 = 83 + 1452.2 + 0 = 1535.2$$

$$G = \max [G_1, G_2, G_3, G_4, G_5, G_6],$$

$$\therefore \text{LB (1-5)} = 1535.2$$

For $J_6 = (1-6)$, then $J' (1-6) = 4.5, 7.7, 11.2, 15, 19, 24$

$$G_1 = 4.5 + 1453 + 13.3 = 1470.8$$

$$G_2 = 7.7 + 1457.7 + 10.8 = 1476.2$$

$$G_3 = 11.2 + 1459.3 + 8 = 1478.2$$

$$G_4 = 15 + 1459.7 + 5.4 = 1480.1$$

$$G_5 = 19 + 1462 + 2.2 = 1483.2$$

$$G_6 = 24 + 1467.2 + 0 = 1491.2$$

$$G = \max [G_1, G_2, G_3, G_4, G_5, G_6],$$

$$\therefore \text{LB (1-6)} = 1491.2$$

Now branch from $J_{1-2} = (1-2)$

For $J_3 = (1-2-3)$, then $J' (1-2-3) = 1443.5, 2883.5, 4323.5, 5763.5, 7203.5, 8643.5$

$$G_1 = 1443.5 + 14 + 19.1 = 1476.6$$

$$G_2 = 2883.5 + 18.4 + 15.9 = 2921.4$$

$$G_3 = 4323.5 + 20 + 12.4 = 4355.9$$

$$G_4 = 5763.5 + 20.9 + 8.8 = 5793.2$$

$$G_5 = 7203.5 + 22.8 + 5 = 7231.3$$

$$G_6 = 8643.5 + 30 + 0 = 8673.5$$

$$G = \max [G_1, G_2, G_3, G_4, G_5, G_6],$$

$$\therefore \text{LB (1-2-3)} = 8673.5$$

For $J_4 = (1-2-4)$, then $J' (1-2-4) = 6.5, 9.7, 13.2, 16.8, 20.6, 25.6$

$$G_1 = 6.5 + 1451 + 19.5 = 1477$$

$$G_2 = 9.7 + 1455.2 + 16.3 = 1481.2$$

$$G_3 = 13.2 + 1456.5 + 12.8 = 1482.5$$

$$G_4 = 16.8 + 1457.3 + 9 = 1483.1$$

$$G_5 = 20.6 + 1459 + 5 = 1484.6$$

$$G_6 = 25.6 + 1465 + 0 = 1490.6$$

$$G = \max [G_1, G_2, G_3, G_4, G_5, G_6],$$

$$\therefore \text{LB (1-2-4)} = 1490.6$$

For $J_5 = (1-2-5)$, then $J' (1-2-5) = 11.5, 23.5, 36.5, 50, 65, 85$.

$$G_1 = 11.5 + 1446 + 19.1 = 1476.6$$

$$G_2 = 23.5 + 1446.4 + 15.9 = 1485.8$$

$$G_3 = 36.5 + 1447 + 12.4 = 1495.9$$

$$G_4 = 50 + 1447.4 + 8.8 = 1506.2$$

$$G_5 = 65 + 1447.8 + 5 = 1517.8$$

$$G_6 = 85 + 1450 + 0 = 1535$$

$$G = \max [G_1, G_2, G_3, G_4, G_5, G_6],$$

$$\therefore \text{LB (1-2-5)} = 1535$$

For $J_6 = (1-2-6)$, then $J' (1-2-6) = 6.5, 9.7, 13.2, 17, 21, 26$.

$$G_1 = 6.5 + 1451 + 19.1 = 1476.6$$

$$G_2 = 9.7 + 1455 + 15.9 = 1480.8$$

$$G_3 = 13.2 + 1456.5 + 12.4 = 1482.1$$

$$G_4 = 17 + 1457.1 + 8.8 = 1482.9$$

$$G_5 = 21 + 1458.8 + 5 = 1484.8$$

$$G_6 = 26 + 1465 + 0 = 1491$$

$$G = \max [G_1, G_2, G_3, G_4, G_5, G_6],$$

$$\therefore \text{LB (1-2-6)} = 1491$$

Now branch from $J_{124} = (1-2-4)$

For $J_4 = (1-2-4-3)$, then $J' (1-2-4-3) = 1446.5, 2886.5, 4326.5, 5766.5, 7206.5, 8646.5$.

$$G_1 = 1446.5 + 11 + 19.5 = 1477$$

$$G_2 = 2886.5 + 15.2 + 16.3 = 2918$$

$$G_3 = 4326.5 + 16.5 + 12.8 = 4355.8$$

$$G_4 = 5766.5 + 17.3 + 9 = 5792.8$$

$$G_5 = 7206.5 + 19 + 5 = 7230.5$$

$$G_6 = 8646.5 + 25 + 0 = 8671.5$$

$$G = \max [G_1, G_2, G_3, G_4, G_5, G_6],$$

$$\therefore \text{LB (1-2-4-3)} = 8671.5$$

For $J_5 = (1-2-4-5)$, then $J' (1-2-4-5) = 14.5, 26.5, 39.5, 53, 68, 88$

$$G_1 = 14.5 + 1443 + 19.5 = 1477$$

$$G_2 = 26.5 + 1443.2 + 16.3 = 1486$$

$$G_3 = 39.5 + 1443.5 + 12.8 = 1495.8$$

$$G_4 = 53 + 1443.8 + 9 = 1505.8$$

$$G_5 = 68 + 1444 + 5 = 1517$$

$$G_6 = 88 + 1445 + 0 = 1533$$

$$G = \max [G_1, G_2, G_3, G_4, G_5, G_6],$$

$$\therefore \text{LB (1-2-4-5)} = 1533$$

For $J_6 = (1-2-4-6)$, then $J' (1-2-4-6) = 9.5, 12.7, 16.2, 20, 24, 29$

$$G_1 = 9.5 + 1448 + 73.5 = 1531$$

$$G_2 = 12.7 + 1452 + 61.5 = 1526.2$$

$$G_3 = 16.2 + 1453 + 48.5 = 1517.7$$

$$G_4 = 20 + 1453.5 + 35 = 1508.5$$

$$G_5 = 24 + 1455 + 20 = 1499$$

$$G_6 = 29 + 1460 + 0 = 1489$$

$$G = \max [G_1, G_2, G_3, G_4, G_5, G_6],$$

$$\therefore \text{LB (1-2-4-6)} = 1531$$

Now branch from $J_{1246} = (1-2-4-6)$

For $J_5 = (1-2-4-6-3)$, then $J' (1-2-4-6-3) = 1449.5, 2889.5, 4329.5, 5769.5, 7209.5, 8649.5$

$$G_1 = 1449.5 + 8 + 73.5 = 1531$$

$$G_2 = 2889.5 + 12 + 61.5 = 2963$$

$$G_3 = 4329.5 + 13 + 48.5 = 4391$$

$$G_4 = 5769.5 + 13.5 + 35 = 5818$$

$$G_5 = 7209.5 + 15 + 20 = 7244.5$$

$$G_6 = 8649.5 + 20 + 0 = 8669.5$$

$$G = \max [G_1, G_2, G_3, G_4, G_5, G_6],$$

$$\therefore \text{LB (1-2-4-6-3)} = 8669.5$$

For $J_5 = (1-2-4-6-5)$, then $J' (1-2-4-6-5) = 17.5, 29.5, 42.5, 56, 71, 91$

$$G_1 = 17.5 + 1440 + 7200 = 8657.5$$

$$G_2 = 29.5 + 1440 + 5760 = 7229.5$$

$$G_3 = 42.5 + 1440 + 4320 = 5802.5$$

$$G_4 = 56 + 1440 + 2880 = 4376$$

$$G_5 = 71 + 1440 + 1440 = 2951$$

$$G_6 = 91 + 1440 + 0 = 1531$$

$$G = \max [G_1, G_2, G_3, G_4, G_5, G_6],$$

$$\therefore \text{LB (1-2-4-6-5)} = 8657.5$$

The lower bounds for respective jobs are as shown in [Table 3](#).

Table 3. Lower bounds for respective jobs

Node (J_r)	LB (J_r)
(1)	1486.1
(2)	1489.5
(3)	8676.4
(4)	1493.5
(5)	1537.9
(6)	1493.9
(1-2)	1486.8
(1-3)	8673.7
(1-4)	1490.8
(1-5)	1535.2
(1-6)	1491.2
(1-2-3)	8673.5
(1-2-4)	1490.6
(1-2-5)	1535
(1-2-6)	1491
(1-2-4-3)	8671.5
(1-2-4-5)	1533
(1-2-4-6)	1531
(1-2-4-6-3)	8669.5
(1-2-4-6-5)	8657.5

The optimal sequence is Job1 – Job2 – Job4 – Job6 – Job5 – Job3.

Step 4:

The in-out tableau is for the optimal sequence obtained in step 3 is as shown in Table 4. It will give the minimum total elapsed time corresponding to the make span.

Table 4. In – out tableau

Job	M ₁ In – out	M ₂ In – out	M ₃ In – out	M ₄ In – out	M ₅ In – out	M ₆ In – out
1	0 – 1.5	1.5 – 3.2	3.2 – 5.1	5.1 – 7.2	7.2 – 9.7	9.7 – 13.9
2	1.5 – 3.5	3.5 – 6.0	6.0 – 8.8	8.8 – 11.4	11.4 – 14.6	14.6 – 16.8
4	3.5 – 6.5	6.5 – 9.7	9.7 – 13.2	13.2 – 16.8	16.8 – 20.6	20.6 – 25.6
6	6.5 – 9.5	9.7 – 12.9	13.2 – 16.7	16.8 – 20.6	20.6 – 24.6	25.6 – 30.6
5	9.5 – 17.5	17.5 – 29.5	29.5 – 42.5	42.5 – 56.0	56.0 – 71.0	71.0 – 91.0
3	17.5 – 1457.5	1457.5 – 2897.5	2897.5 – 4337.5	4337.5 – 5777.5	5777.5 – 7217.5	7217.5 – 8657.5

Hence, the total elapsed time is 8657.5mins. The flow shop branching tree diagram is as shown in Fig. 2.

Fig.2 Flow-shop Branching Tree

In this research work, branch and bound approach was used in solving flow-shop problem. We considered flow-shop problem with make-span criterion and the research data were obtained from Mouka Foam Nigeria Limited, Benin City, Nigeria. The data were presented and analyzed. The data comprised the processing time of six jobs (different sizes of foam) to six machines in the production processes of Mouka Foam. It was realized that the optimal sequence of the analyzed data is Job1-Job2-Job4-Job6-Job5-Job3. Finally, it was revealed from the research that the total elapsed time or make-span is 8657.5mins.

CONCLUSION

In this present work, we carried out analysis and application of Branch and Bound Technique for minimizing the make-span of a flow shop. The study mathematical computations and analysis revealed that branch and bound approach is effective tools for solving flow-shop problems. The evaluation has a great contribution to Mouka Foam Nigeria Limited in sequencing its jobs to machines for optimality.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

There is no conflict of interest associated with this research work.

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